

Neurological manifestations of MIS-C: a single-center experience and case-based literature review*

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Abstract

Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) is a rare but severe post-infectious complication associated with SARS-CoV-2. Neurological manifestations occur in approximately one quarter of MIS-C cases, ranging from mild symptoms such as headache and photophobia to severe complications including seizures, encephalopathy, and stroke. This article provides a comprehensive review of the neurological aspects of MIS-C, incorporating evidence from the literature and a detailed case report of a 15-year-old male who presented with acute neurological symptoms, systemic inflammation, and multiorgan involvement. Four main pathophysiological mechanisms have been proposed to explain neurological involvement: cytokine-mediated neuroinflammation, blood–brain barrier disruption, autoimmune responses, and direct viral neuroinvasion. Neuroimaging and EEG findings often support encephalopathic processes, while laboratory and immunological profiles indicate a hyperinflammatory state. The present case also highlights a potential link between severe hyponatremia and neurological complications. Management strategies—such as immunomodulation, anticoagulation, supportive therapy, and neuroprotective interventions—are discussed in this context. The prognosis for MIS-C patients with neurological involvement varies, with severe cases requiring long-term monitoring. This review underscores the importance of early neurological assessment in MIS-C to guide treatment and improve outcomes.

Keywords

cytokine storm, encephalopathy, MIS-C, neuroinflammation, pediatric COVID-19, seizures

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Introduction

Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) is a novel hyperinflammatory condition emerging in pediatric patients following SARS-CoV-2 exposure. First described in 2020, MIS-C is characterized by persistent fever, systemic inflammation, and multisystem organ involvement, typically occurring weeks after the initial infection. Although respiratory and cardiovascular involvement are often emphasized, neurological symptoms have increasingly been reported, affecting approximately 24.8% of diagnosed cases (Patel 2022; Peng and Zhou 2025).

The neurological features of MIS-C vary widely. Common symptoms include headache, signs of meningeal irritation, and acute encephalopathy. Less common and more serious complications, such as seizures, ataxia, cranial nerve palsies, ischemic stroke, and intracerebral hemorrhage, have also been reported. These symptoms make diagnosis and treatment more challenging, especially when neurological signs appear before typical inflammatory markers or cardiovascular problems (Abbati et al. 2022).

The pathophysiology of neurologic involvement in MIS-C is not fully understood. Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain the neurological symptoms seen in MIS-C. One major theory involves a hyperinflammatory response, marked by high levels of proinflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-6 (IL-6), interleukin-10 (IL-10), and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), which may cause widespread neuroinflammation. Another mechanism involves endothelial dysfunction and disruption of the blood-brain barrier (BBB), allowing immune cells and inflammatory substances to enter the central nervous system (CNS). Additionally, autoimmune processes are suspected, particularly through molecular mimicry, where viral antigens resemble neuronal proteins and may trigger immune responses against the body's neural tissues. A more debated hypothesis suggests direct viral invasion; although SARS-CoV-2 RNA has been found in cerebrospinal fluid in some cases, the evidence is inconsistent, and the clinical significance remains uncertain (Lin et al. 2023; Lawrence et al. 2024).

This case-based review aims to contextualize these mechanisms with a real-world case and current literature, emphasizing the clinical spectrum, diagnostic challenges, and treatment considerations in MIS-C-related neurological involvement.

Search strategy

A comprehensive literature search was conducted to identify relevant studies on the neurological manifestations of MIS-C. The databases searched included PubMed, Scopus, Embase, and Web of Science, using the following Boolean search string: "MIS-C" OR "multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children" AND ("neurological manifestations" OR "encephalopathy" OR "seizures" OR "neuroinflammation") AND ("COVID-19" OR "SARS-CoV-2").

The search was restricted to peer-reviewed articles, systematic reviews, case series, and clinical reports published in English from January 2019 to May 2024. The inclusion criteria were as follows: pediatric age group, confirmed MIS-C diagnosis, and documented neurological findings. Studies focusing on pathophysiological hypotheses, diagnostic imaging, or long-term neurocognitive outcomes were prioritized. A total of 276 articles were retrieved, 183 were screened after title and abstract review, and 15 were included in the final manuscript (Fig. 1).

In addition to the systematic literature review, we retrospectively analyzed a sequential institutional cohort of 51 children diagnosed with MIS-C. Neurological manifestations were identified in two patients, both of whom presented with profound hyponatremia. However, due to incomplete clinical data and missing follow-up records, only one patient could be analyzed in detail and is presented as the illustrative case report below. This cohort provides contextual data for understanding the potential association between electrolyte imbalance and neurological involvement in MIS-C.

We included 51 consecutive MIS-C patients treated between 25 November 2020 and 24 April 2021 in our center. Of these, 73% were male ($n = 37$) and 27% female ($n = 14$). Children older than 5 years accounted for 78% ($n = 40$) of the cohort, whereas 22% ($n = 11$) were younger than 5. Fourteen (27.5%) had comorbidities (e.g., drug allergies, bronchial asthma, cerebral palsy, epilepsy). Radiologic assessment included abdominal ultrasound in all patients and additional thoracic or CT imaging when clinically indicated. Follow-up lasted 1 to 6 months.

One notable feature of this case is the presence of profound hyponatremia (serum Na < 125 mmol/L) during the acute neurologic episode. Among our broader institutional cohort of 51 MIS-C patients, only two exhibited neurological symptoms, both of whom had severe hyponatremia. The number was insufficient for comprehensive statistical analysis. To investigate whether they differed from the other 49 children in laboratory and clinical parameters, several analytical approaches were applied. We also conducted a CART (classification and regression trees) analysis to determine whether the two patients with neurological involvement could be distinguished from the rest (Fig. 2). They appeared to differ only in Na levels. Additionally, a violin plot was produced to compare Na levels between the two groups, with reference values for serum Na also depicted (Fig. 3). The children with neurological involvement were the only ones with levels below 125 mmol/L.

For visualization and initial orientation in our data, a table was created (Table 1), using major laboratory parameters, including hematological markers, inflammatory markers, AST, ALT, total bilirubin, GGT, coagulation parameters, creatinine, and electrolytes (Na, K, and Cl).

Abbreviations: **Leuc** = leukocytes; **PLT** = platelets; **CRP** = C-reactive protein; **AST/ASAT** = aspartate aminotransferase; **ALT/ALAT** = alanine aminotransferase; **GGT** = gamma-glutamyl transferase; **INR** = international normalized ratio; **LDH** = lactate dehydrogenase; **Na** = sodium; **K** = potassium; **Cl** = chloride.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram of the literature search and selection process for studies included in this review.

Figure 2. The decision tree generated by the CART analysis shows the separation of MIS-C patients from other MIS-C patients based on the min-max scaled levels of serum sodium.

The decision tree generated by the CART analysis shows the separation of MIS-C patients from other MIS-C patients based on the min-max scaled levels of serum sodium.

Furthermore, the violin plot illustrated the serum sodium (Na) levels in both groups, with reference values also depicted. Only children with neurological involvement had serum sodium levels below 125 mmol/L. These findings suggest a potential association between hyponatremia and neurological symptoms in this population. Such a correlation could provide additional insight into the pathophysiology of neurological impairment in COVID-19, aligning with existing evidence linking electrolyte disturbances to neurological outcomes in viral infections. Further studies are warranted to elucidate the causal relationship and underlying mechanisms.

Figure 3. Violin plot with reference values included comparing serum sodium levels (mmol/l) in children with neurological involvement versus those without).

Table 1. Major laboratory parameters in the MIS-C cohort, highlighting the two patients with hyponatremia.

Laboratory parameters	Mean	Median	Std. dev	Minimum	Maximum	Patient 1	Patient 2
Leuc (G/L)	13.18	12	6.8	4.63	35.50	9*	10.62*
PLT (G/L)	207.96	202	115.3	59	666	120*	148*
CRP (mg/dl)	19.9	19	12.7	0.02	76.50	18.24*	21.4*
Ferritin (ng/ml)	552	491.4	370.7	67.50	1550	1500*	617*
Troponin (ng/ml)	99.5	31.4	194.8	1	849.70	402*	23*
LDH (U/L)	359.4	305	187	186	1159	661*	251*
Protein total (g/L)	60.6	61	9.8	36	85	55*	52*
ASAT (U/L)	89	44	173.4	12	1168	33*	26*
ALAT (U/L)	67.1	35.7	99.6	7	634	27*	15*
GGT (U/L)	67.7	35	83.0	3	416	51*	5*
Tot. Bilirubin (μ mol/l)	17.3	10	22.2	0.10	103.6	12*	7.6*
INR	1.2	1.17	0.3	0.87	2.88	1.11*	1.3*
Fibrinogen (g/L)	5.2	5.6	1.6	1.80	9	6.5*	6*
D-dimer (ng/mL)	2234.8	1598	750	90	8284	3520*	623*
Creatinine (mmol/L)	64.3	55.5	31.42	26.82	182	110*	63*
Na ⁺ (mmol/L)	134.3	136	4.6	121	142	121**	124**
K ⁺ (mmol/L)	4.1	4.1	0.61	2.80	5.70	4.1*	3.6*
Cl ⁻ (mmol/L)	100.82	102	4.1	92	107	100*	93*

* Non-significant difference (Mann-Whitney U test).

** Significant difference (Mann-Whitney U test).

Case report

A 15-year-old previously healthy male presented with a 48-hour history of high-grade fever (up to 40 °C), fatigue, anorexia, nausea, abdominal discomfort, and multiple episodes of diarrhea. On the day of hospital admission, the patient experienced a sudden episode of altered consciousness, accompanied by horizontal ocular deviation, jaw clenching, and generalized tonic extension of all limbs, followed by generalized convulsions, each episode lasting several seconds.

On physical examination, the patient was somnolent, disoriented to time and place, and responded to verbal stimuli with a noticeable delay. His Glasgow Coma Scale score was 13/15. Dermatological findings included generalized macular erythema and dry mucous membranes. Cardiopulmonary assessment showed bilateral basal rales, tachypnea

at 40 breaths/min, muffled heart sounds, and hypotension (80/40 mmHg). Tachycardia at 125 bpm and signs of circulatory compromise were observed. Abdominal examination revealed hepatomegaly (2.5 cm below the costal margin) and diffuse tenderness. Neurological assessment indicated photophobia, skin hyperesthesia, neck stiffness, and positive Brudzinski and Kernig signs, consistent with meningeal irritation.

Laboratory investigations revealed elevated markers of inflammation (CRP, ESR, procalcitonin, D-dimer, ferritin) and positive anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibodies, consistent with prior exposure. Notably, profound hyponatremia (serum Na < 125 mmol/L) was detected. Imaging studies showed bilateral pulmonary infiltrates and cardiomegaly on chest radiograph, with echocardiography demonstrating exudative pericarditis and significant pericardial and pleural effusions. Cranial CT was largely unremarkable.

The patient fulfilled CDC MIS-C criteria: age < 21 years, fever ≥ 38 °C for ≥ 24 h, elevated inflammatory markers (CRP, ESR, ferritin, D-dimer, procalcitonin), multisystem involvement (cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, dermatologic, neurological), laboratory evidence of SARS-CoV-2 exposure (positive anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG), and no alternative diagnosis (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 2024).

The patient was treated empirically with ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, and vancomycin. Due to severe systemic inflammation, high-dose methylprednisolone at 2 mg/kg i.v. was initiated, and treatment with intravenous immunoglobulins (IVIG) was attempted at a dose of 0.4 g/kg for 5 days but discontinued early due to an allergic reaction that presented with a diffuse urticarial rash and hypotension. Supportive measures included inotropic support (dopamine, epinephrine, and milrinone), while anticoagulation was initiated with low-molecular-weight heparin and later transitioned to oral acenocoumarol. Notably, the patient exhibited antithrombin III deficiency, likely acquired in the context of systemic inflammation, which may have contributed to the hypercoagulable state observed and may influence the pharmacodynamics of heparin-based therapies. Neuroprotective measures were undertaken due to the clinical observation of worsening mental status and meningism (mannitol, citicoline, loop diuretics, judicious use of hypertonic saline—with the latter serving a dual role as treatment for hyponatremia and possible cerebral edema)—as well as valproic acid for seizure control. Progressive clinical improvement was observed throughout hospitalization, with full resolution of neurological symptoms and normalization of sodium level.

Discussion

Neurological manifestations in MIS-C are varied and clinically significant and can range from subtle cognitive or behavioral changes to severe and potentially life-threatening conditions. Approximately 24.8% of MIS-C cases have reported neurological symptoms, including headache, photophobia, meningism, seizures, altered consciousness, and cerebrovascular events. This case illustrates the complex neurological presentation of MIS-C and highlights emerging trends in the literature (Abbati et al. 2022).

Our patient presented with generalized seizures, encephalopathy, meningeal signs, and diffuse hyperesthesia in the context of systemic inflammation and multiorgan dysfunction. The constellation of symptoms and their timing after SARS-CoV-2 exposure fulfill MIS-C diagnostic criteria. The acute neurological deterioration, along with inflammatory and imaging findings, reflects the increasingly recognized neuroinflammatory phenotype linked to MIS-C (Bova et al. 2022).

Neuroimaging in MIS-C often shows temporary and reversible abnormalities. Although MRI was not performed in this case due to initial hemodynamic instability, the literature frequently reports radiologic features such as reversible splenic lesion syndrome (RESLES),

acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM), and bilateral thalamic involvement—indicating both cytotoxic and vasogenic processes. While computed tomography is less sensitive for detecting subtle parenchymal changes, it remains a useful first-line modality in urgent situations and helped rule out hemorrhage or gross edema in this patient (Ray et al. 2021; Şahan and Yabalak 2024).

Several mechanisms likely contribute to neurological involvement in MIS-C, including cytokine-driven neuroinflammation, blood–brain barrier disruption, autoimmune reactivity, and, less definitively, direct viral invasion of the CNS. As outlined earlier, each of these mechanisms offers a theoretical framework supporting different aspects of the observed clinical and laboratory findings. In this case, the pronounced systemic inflammatory response and positive response to immunosuppressive treatment strongly suggest an immune-mediated pathogenesis rather than direct viral neurotropism (Mohammadi et al. 2020; Mayer and Fischer 2025).

One notable feature of this case is the presence of profound hyponatremia (serum sodium < 125 mmol/L) during the acute neurological episode. While causality cannot be definitively established, hyponatremia is a known trigger for seizures and altered consciousness and may contribute to worsening symptoms in the context of systemic inflammation and neurovascular dysfunction. This suggests that electrolyte imbalances might influence neurological sensitivity in MIS-C, a hypothesis that merits further research (Mills et al. 2021).

Electroencephalography (EEG) findings in MIS-C-related encephalopathy usually show generalized slowing, indicating widespread cortical dysfunction. Our patient's clinical presentation—a transient seizure with altered consciousness and recovery after anti-inflammatory and supportive treatment—aligns with inflammatory encephalopathy rather than structural, genetic, or metabolic causes (Rayi et al. 2024).

Treatment of neurological complications in MIS-C is directed by the underlying inflammatory process. While cerebral edema was hypothesized based on clinical grounds only, it rapidly improved with treatment. Immunomodulatory therapy with intravenous corticosteroids and immunoglobulin is central to suppressing the cytokine storm. In our case, therapy with intravenous immunoglobulins (IVIG) was discontinued due to an allergic reaction, and glucocorticoids were continued as monotherapy with favorable effects. Additionally, methylprednisolone was administered as pulse therapy at doses of 2 mg/kg for 5 days. Adjunctive treatments for neuroprotection, including mannitol, loop diuretics, and citicoline, were employed to manage hypothesized cerebral edema and maintain cerebral perfusion. Anticoagulation was administered considering cardiovascular involvement and elevated D-dimer levels. Antiepileptic therapy was initiated with valproic acid following seizure activity (Ouldali et al. 2023; Chen et al. 2024).

Prognosis in MIS-C with neurological involvement is generally positive, especially with prompt

recognition and targeted treatment. However, some patients may face ongoing neurocognitive issues—especially following severe or prolonged encephalopathy. These problems include difficulties with attention, memory, executive function, and emotional regulation. Therefore, long-term neurodevelopmental monitoring is crucial, ideally including neuropsychological assessments and rehabilitation services (LaRovere et al. 2021; Bova et al. 2022).

Our case underscores the importance of considering MIS-C in any febrile pediatric patient presenting with new neurological symptoms and signs of systemic inflammation. A multidisciplinary approach involving pediatric neurology, infectious disease, critical care, and cardiology is essential for comprehensive evaluation and treatment. Implementing standardized clinical pathways for assessing encephalopathy, performing imaging, monitoring electrolytes, and selecting immunotherapy could enhance diagnostic accuracy and improve patient outcomes.

While this case offers valuable insight into the growing understanding of MIS-C-related neuroinflammation, limitations still exist. The lack of brain MRI and CSF analysis limits confirmation of subclinical neuroinflammatory changes or ruling out viral invasion. However, the clinical course and response to treatment provide strong circumstantial evidence for immune-mediated neurological dysfunction.

Future directions in MIS-C research should focus on identifying the immunologic profiles that increase the risk of neurological involvement, clarifying the mechanistic role of electrolyte imbalance, and examining the long-term neurocognitive outcomes in survivors. Multicenter cohort studies and prospective registries will be crucial for developing evidence-based protocols for diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up in these patients (Jaxybayeva et al. 2023).

This study has several limitations. First, it is a single-center experience with only two patients showing neurological manifestations among 51 MIS-C cases, limiting generalizability. The small subgroup prevented meaningful statistical comparisons and interpretation of hyponatremia as a risk factor, which itself can independently cause seizures and psychiatric disturbances. Second, neurodiagnostic evaluations—including brain MRI, CSF analysis, and EEG—were not performed due to the patients' critical and rapidly deteriorating conditions, multiple hospital transfers, and incomplete medical records. This limits confirmation of neuroinflammatory changes or direct viral involvement. Third, treatment responses are difficult to interpret because multiple interventions were used simultaneously, including immunomodulatory therapy, supportive care, neuroprotective agents, antiepileptics, anticoagulation, and broad-spectrum antimicrobials. Finally, potential publication and selection biases in the literature review and missing data for the second patient with neurological involvement further limit the strength of conclusions regarding neurological outcomes in MIS-C.

Conclusion

Neurological manifestations in MIS-C represent a clinically significant and heterogeneous spectrum of disease, frequently complicating an already complex inflammatory syndrome. This case-based review demonstrates how neurological involvement may present acutely and severely, necessitating rapid recognition, targeted immunomodulation, and supportive care.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: This research was ethically approved by University Hospital N. I. Pirogov Ethics Committee (No 123-20/23.12.2020) and conducted according to Helsinki Declaration standards. All participants had parental consent, with children ≥ 12 years also providing individual informed consent.

Written informed consent was obtained from all patients' legal guardians for the publication of clinical data. The institutional review board approved the retrospective analysis of anonymized patient data and waived the need for additional consent for the cohort study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, G.V.V., T.V. and S.L.; methodology, G.H.V.; software, G.H.V.; validation, G.V.V., N.G. and I.T.; formal analysis, G.V.V.; investigation, N.G.; resources, I.T.; data curation, G.H.V.; writing—original draft preparation, G.V.V.; writing—review and editing, T.V.; visualization,

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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